

Extending COVID Risk Assessment Models with Ambient Sensors

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Abstract

COVID-19 pandemic has caused great loss in humanity. While its impacts on public health and socio-economy have been less severe, it is important to quantify the risk of infection for decision making. COVID Airborne Risk Assessment Calculator (CARA) is a web interface assessment tool developed by Henriques and colleagues from CERN. This study explores the possibility to extend the model by connecting it to sensors and supplying with updated indoor environmental data, with an ambition to improve the practicality and reliability of the model and create a sensor device that can communicate risk with occupants.

In addition, carbon dioxide (CO₂) is a common indicator for indoor air quality, ventilation, and even risk for airborne transmissible disease. This study attempts to incorporate data collected from a CO₂ sensor for ventilation estimation and supply it as a parameter for the CARA model. Furthermore, a CO₂-based transmission model from Rudnick & Milton was deployed for risk assessment with simple set up.

This study has shown the feasibility in creating a sensor device for airborne risk assessment using a comprehensive or a simple model. It also promotes risk communication in multiple levels by creating multiple visualizations including sensor display and data dashboard. While focusing on COVID-19, the approach can be extended to other airborne transmissible diseases.

Declaration of Authorship

I, Wing Hong OR, confirm that the work presented in this assessment is my own. Where information has been derived from other sources, I confirm that this has been indicated in the work. The dissertation is 5,950 words in length.

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1. Introduction

COVID-19 has caused severe casualties and profoundly affected communication, business, and lifestyle on all scales. According to World Health Organization (2022), the number of confirmed deaths is above 6.4 million. However, the excess mortality from the pandemic in 2020 and 2021 may reach 18.2 million (COVID-19 Excess Mortality Collaborators 2022). Despite the introduction and wild adoption of vaccines, it is still considered a major health threat and measures such as travel ban on foreign nationals, quarantine and even lockdown are still implemented in some places. In the long term, it is expected that COVID-19 will have a lower health impact but will stay and become a recurrent disease (Murray 2022). To minimize the health impact, infection risk assessment tools could be used to support facility managers, and building engineers for building design and ventilation, as well as supporting decisions such as indoor face mask mandates and number of people allowed within a premise.

Henriques et al. (2022) from CERN have developed a calculator (COVID Airborne Risk Assessment Calculator, CARA), which accepts inputs such as the number of infected people and total occupants within the premise, the dimension, ventilation, and function of the venue, as well as whether masks are worn, and provides a probability of getting infected. The model incorporates physical, mechanical and biological aspects and focuses on virological and immunological concerns.

Nowadays many offices or institutions are equipped with indoor air quality sensors. These sensors provide a low-cost monitoring solution and support evidence-based decision making. Since COVID has become a major health concern, it is purposed to create a sensor device for the same reasons. The research question of this project is:

Does incorporating sensors enhance COVID risk assessment?

This project aims at exploring the possibility to extend the CARA model from a web-based calculation tool to a sensor device that support automatic risk assessment with updated parameter values. It further investigates the utilization of a CO₂ sensor and occupant-generated CO₂ data in airborne transmissible risk assessment. This includes an indirect application as an air change rate parameter in CARA calculation, and a direct application as a proxy of exhaled breathe in Rudnick-Milton's model. Last but not least, this project attempts to communicate risk in multiple levels, from the on-device display to a building management perspective.

The next chapter (Chapter 2) provides a literature review related to airborne infection transmission assessment and ventilation estimation. Chapter 3 describes the procedures in software programming and physical device making. Chapter 4 discusses the outcomes and performance of the devices as well as provides a critical reflection. Chapter 5 concludes the project by reinstating the contribution and recommendations for future works.

2. Literature Review

A risk assessment tool allows comparison of infection probability in different scenarios, a cost-benefit analysis can then be performed to identify measures that can achieve an acceptable risk level with minimal additional cost (Ellis 2021). Airborne transmission has been identified as the major way of transmission for SARS-CoV-2, even in close range situation exposure by inhalation is more likely than direct contact (Tang et al. 2021). Initially developed for internal building management, the COVID Airborne Risk Assessment (Henriques et al., 2022) is available to the public via GitHub (<https://github.com/CERN/cara>). The model considers 5 aspects: source, dispersion, exposure, dose, and risk. It receives inputs related to the virus (such as virus type), infected and exposed persons (such as their number, vocal activity and whether masks are worn), and environment (such as dimensions of the room and ventilation rate). The infection probability is generated by Monte Carlo method. A further introduction of the model is available in Appendix A.

Apart from CARA model, there are other indoor airborne transmission risk models, including the extensively used Wells-Riley model from Riley et al. (1978). It is based on quantum generation rate which refers to the rate of generating an amount of bacteria/ virus that will cause an infection. Many other models built on top of Wells-Riley model, such as the COVID-19 Aerosol Transmission Estimator from Jimenez & Peng (2021), and the inclusion of the spatial flow impact factor into the model by Guo, et al. (2021). There are also risk calculators in the form of apps that inform users with the numerical or relative risk of contracting, getting infected, or dying from COVID-19, based on information about location, personal conditions, activity, and venue setting. For example, *MyCOVIDRisk* was developed on top of a transmission estimator from Jimenez & Peng (2021), while *COVID-19 Mortality Risk Calculator* was based on the mortality statistics from the Center of Disease Control (Eisenstein 2020). These calculators put the emphasis on personal characteristics and suit individual usage.

Measuring ventilation is important for indoor air quality assessment, and in the time of pandemic, risk quantification. Tracer gas methods are commonly used for ventilation measurement. Tracer gas techniques can be categorized into transient methods such as decay techniques, which measure air change rate, and steady-state methods which measure ventilation flow, such as pulse, constant injection, long term integral, and constant concentration (Sherman 1990). There are other methods in assessing ventilation such as measuring pressure difference, but these would require specific equipment such as pressure taps as well as knowledge of discharge coefficient (Gough et al. 2018). For the decay technique, a tracer gas is released into a room until a uniform concentration is reached. Assuming a constant air change rate, there will be an exponential decay in tracer gas concentration and that rate is the air change rate of the space in units of inverse time. The single-zone mass balance approach is used in this technique as well as other methods such as constant injection and constant concentration (Persily 2016). It is also commonly referred in indoor air contaminant assessment, such as for the development of an indoor CO₂ metric analysis tool (Persily & Polidoro 2022). A range of gases were used as tracer gas for ventilation study such as sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and methane (CH₄) (Dajose 2021). Nevertheless, there are concerns in using these tracer gases. For one thing, these gases

are all greenhouse gasses and contribute to global warming, particularly for SF₆ which has a greenhouse gas potential 28500 times greater than CO₂ (Myhre et al. 2013). They are also specific requirements such as a proper mixing system or a vapour compensation (Niemelä et al. 1991, Laporte et al. 2001). Apart from injecting additional tracer gas, occupants exhale CO₂ in their breath and that could be considered as a tracer gas for ventilation assessment. Decay method using occupant-generated CO₂ was found to be more favourable than using SF₆ as tracer gas or measuring air flow in ventilation ducts, while integral method using occupant-generated CO₂ would overestimate the ventilation rate if ventilation is achieved by air recirculation (Turiel & Rudy 1980).

Apart from being considered as a tracer gas for ventilation, occupant exhaled CO₂ is further considered to be an infection risk proxy, as similar to aerosols containing virus, CO₂ is exhaled from the infected and inhaled by the exposed (Peng & Jimenez 2021). This re-emphasises the importance of adequate ventilation. Rudnick & Milton (2002) have derived a CO₂-based equation to estimate indoor airborne transmission risk. In contrast to Wells-Riley equation it does not demand an assumption that the quantum concentration and ventilation rate have reached steady state.

3. Methodology

3.1 Model hosting and adjustment

The GitHub repository from CERN (<https://github.com/CERN/cara>) containing the official CARA model was forked into author's repository to enable edition and testing. The instructions for running CARA on a Raspberry Pi from Devine (2021) was generally followed to host the assessment tool on local network. In brief, this included first the installation of Python3.9 and some packages, and then cloning the GitHub repository containing the model, installing it in Pi and running it. Furthermore, a service unit was written in *systemd* to run the model at start-up.

Some adjustments were made to the CARA model to serve this project. Firstly, each POST request from the microcontroller to the Pi took a considerable amount of time to return and is not suitable for a physical device with regular update. To speed up the process, the assessment result was constrained and only information that was used for analysis and display was retained, including the infection probability and emission rate. Other outputs such as temporal concentration was excluded. Another modification is the creation of an addition type of ventilation (*measured ventilation*), taking the minimal air change through infiltration into account. This ventilation type requires only one value which is air change rate and omits sub-parameters such as the number and dimension of windows as well as the duration and extend they are opened. This allows the model to accept air change rate estimated from the CO₂ decay rate and be widely adapted to rooms with different window setting. The modified GitHub repository (<https://github.com/WingHongCASACE/cara>) was clone and installed on the Pi.

3.2 Sensor device design and building

The first version sensor device has a microcontroller, input sensors, and a screen for output display. NodeMCU ESP8266 was selected as the microcontroller for its number of pins and Wi-Fi capability. The sensor components consist of a DHT22 to collect temperature and humidity data, and a T6713 CO₂ Sensor Module to collect CO₂ data. This project did not involve the collection of any personal identifiable data. A 4.2" (10.7 cm) e-Paper Display Module with 400x300 resolutions was chosen as the primary visualization tool for the device. The large screen size allows displaying multiple messages with details. Based on the stable implementation from the first version, a rotary encoder button (EC 11) was added to the device as the second iteration to explore user-device interactivity. This iteration was an attempt to facilitate control and promote flexibility, avoiding the need of unplugging the device and uploading a new coding sketch. Figure 3.1 shows the schematic of both iterations.

Figure 3.1 Schematic for sensor device iteration 1 (top) and iteration 2 (top)

For each version of sensor device, a printed circuit board (PCB) was created to affix and connect electronic components (Figure 3.2). The boards were designed using Autodesk Eagle and outsourced to Seeed Studio for manufacturing. Components were attached onto the PCBs by direct soldering or via pin headers (Figure 3.3). A 4.7k Ω pull up resistor was required for DHT22 and T6713 sensors, respectively.

Figure 3.2 Top view (above) and bottom view (below) of PCB version1 (left) and version 2 (right)

Figure 3.3 PCB with pin headers and resistors (left) and further with electric components (right)

Enclosures were designed to hold the device and assist presentation. Laser cutting and 3D printing techniques were explored, two cases were designed and created for the two versions of device (Figure 3.4). For the laser-cut enclosure, a template of plywood box was generated from Boxes.py with specified dimensions. The template was then exported and modified in Inkscape, such as to create slots to place the PCB and allow the insertion of a MicroUSB connector, before being cut into pieces and assembled into a box.

Figure 3.4 Top: Laser-cut plywood enclosure: exterior (left) and interior (right);
Bottom: 3D-printed enclosure: front view (left) and rear view (right)

Furthermore, a model was designed using Autodesk Fusion 360 for 3D printing to contain the device with a button. It was an original design containing two parts: the base fixes the PCB and display, while the front covers the interior and holes the button (Figure 3.5).

Figure 3.5 3D-printed enclosure with slots to hold PCB and e-Paper (left) and rotary encoder (right)

3.3 Sensor device programming for CARA model

Sketches were developed on Arduino Software IDE and subsequently uploaded to and run on the NodeMCU. The sketches include multiple functions, such as reading sensors' value, configuring the interface of e-Paper, and connecting to the same Wi-Fi network that the

Raspberry Pi is connected to. Further, the NodeMCU communicates to the CARA server by sending POST requests containing pairs of parameters and values for calculation.

Some parameters that were specific to the testing premise were hard coded into the sketch, such as activity type, virus type, and location. Room volume is another example which was obtained using a laser distance measure. Indoor temperature, humidity, and air change per hour were set as variables which got adjusted depending on the sensor readings. Some parameters were not adjusted and remained as default, such as the infected person stays in the room for the whole working day from 8:30 a.m. until 5:30 p.m. For simplicity some CARA default parameters were adjusted, such as value indicating no coffee break or lunch break was assigned. The model was run for a total of 10 occupants in the room, among them one was infected.

Four conditions were assessed: 1.) mask mandated and the exposed persons stay in the room for the current hour, 2.) mask mandated and the exposed persons stay in the room for the whole working day, 3.) no one wears mask and the exposed persons stay in the room for the current hour, and 4.) no one wears mask and the exposed persons stay in the room for the whole working day. The start time and end time of exposure, as well as whether masks were worn, were adjusted depend on the scenario the POST request is about.

For each loop, four POST requests were sent to the CARA server. Once the POST request returns values from the CARA model, selected information is published to MQTT as a serialized JSON object for further application such as data storage, centralized monitoring and management. Originally showing an icon or a project description, the e-Paper display will refresh and show the updated infection probability for each scenario.

The sketches as well as 3D models are available on GitHub (<https://github.com/WingHongCASACE/caraDevice>).

3.4 Inclusion of CO₂ data as ventilation approximate in assessment using CARA model

The department has three commercial indoor environmental sensors on the same floor which records CO₂, temperature and humidity, as well as air pressure. 110 days of CO₂ readings in 10 minutes interval from a sensor installed in the classroom were collected and analysed for an initial understanding of CO₂ behaviour in the room. It was observed that the peak of CO₂ usually occurs between 3 to 5 p.m., followed by an exponential decay. On the following day CO₂ begins to rise after 7 to 9 a.m. and completes a cycle (Figure 3.6). During weekend when the room is always empty, the indoor CO₂ is stable and close to ambient. Therefore, the decay from Friday night/ Saturday midnight may still show the highest CO₂ concentration in weekend (Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.6 CO₂ concentrations in May 2022 as a demonstration of weekly trend in classroom

Figure 3.7 Distribution of daily high and daily low during weekday and weekend

Based on the findings from the commercial CO₂ sensor, it was decided to take the CO₂ concentrations from T6713 CO₂ Sensors in each sensor device at 9 p.m. and 7 a.m. for daily ventilation estimation using equation:

$$ACH = \frac{-1 \cdot \ln \left(\frac{C_{end} - C_{ambient}}{C_{start} - C_{ambient}} \right)}{\Delta t}, \text{ where:}$$

ACH is air change rate (h⁻¹), *C_{end}* and *C_{start}* is the CO₂ concentrations at 9 p.m. and 7 a.m., respectively. *C_{ambient}* is the background outdoor CO₂ concentration which was set at 400ppm. Δt is the time difference which is 10 hours. This equation was promoted by Allen et al. (2020) in assessing ventilation rates in classrooms. The timings were selected to ensure no users are

at the premises during this period, and CO₂ has passed the plateau and is in an exponential decay trend. Furthermore, the whole building was empty at this interval, so measurement avoided the inclusion of occupant-generated CO₂ from adjacent compartment, which was identified as a source of cross-contamination (Almeida et al. 2020). For simplicity, it was assumed that the ventilation rate obtained from the previously night to next day morning is representable for the whole next day. Each POST request sent from NodeMCUs to the CARA model hosted by the Pi has air change rate as the value of parameter *measured ventilation*, which was updated every morning.

3.5 Inclusion of CO₂ data as biomarker of exhaled breath in assessment using Rudnick-Milton's CO₂-based model

Since a CO₂ sensor was incorporated in the device it made sense to look alternative risk models that incorporate CO₂ directly. The Rudnick-Milton's model was selected for its availability of parameters' input, reliance on CO₂ data, relative simplicity, and the stance of not assuming steady state conditions or a constant ventilation rate. For derivation of equation see Rudnick & Milton (2003). The infection probability can be computed using equation:

$$P = \frac{D}{S} = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\bar{f}lqt}{n}\right) \quad , \text{ where:}$$

P is the infection probability for susceptible, D and S is the number of disease cases and susceptible, respectively. \bar{f} is the time-weighted average fraction of exhaled breath in indoor air, which is the difference between volume fraction of CO₂ in indoor and outdoor air, divided by the volume fraction of CO₂ in exhaled breath increased from breathing, which is 0.038 for low oxygen consumption activities such as office work. The difference between volume fraction of CO₂ in indoor and outdoor air was further divided by a million to convert to unit ppm, which is the unit for CO₂ sensor readings. In short,

$$\bar{f} = \frac{CO_2 - 400}{(1000000 * 0.038)} .$$

l and n is the number of infectors and total occupants, respectively. t is the length of exposure and q is the quantum generation rate. While quantum generation rate can be looked up from the literature, for consistency and for the availability of a value for the mask scenario, it was obtained directly from the CARA model by dividing the emission rate returned from CARA assessment by the product of number of infectors and infectious dose (which was set to be 50 in the CARA model).

Observation of results reveals the emission rate is between the range of 1000 – 1100 virions h⁻¹ for no mask scenario, the corresponding quantum generation rate is between 20 – 22 quanta h⁻¹. Such values are very close to the best fit basic quantum generation rate of 18.6 quanta h⁻¹ obtained by Peng et al. (2022), which was accepted by the COVID-19 Aerosol Transmission Estimator developed by Jimenez & Peng (2021) for calculation.

The four scenarios calculated in CARA model were also computed using Rudnick-Milton's model. The emission rates obtained from the four POST request sent to CARA server for risk calculation was used to calculate the risk in Rudnick-Milton's model. Two iterations were performed for the implementation of Rudnick-Milton's model on a sensor device. In the first

iteration the most recent CO₂ level was used to represent the CO₂ level for the whole exposure time. This represents the most simple and lightweight calculation. The second iteration applied time weighted integration and represents a more detailed calculation.

3.6 Visualization and communication

Each sensor device has a 4.2" (10.7 cm) e-Paper display which shows the risk assessment with sensor inputs from the device itself. The display shows a 2x2 table which lists the combination of infection when occupants are with/ without mask and if the exposure is staying in the room for the current hour verse the entire working day, which is from 8.30 a.m. to 5.30 p.m. (Figure 3.8).

Figure 3.8 Risk matrix on e-Paper display

Apart from risk communication on screen, data from each device is serialized as a JSON payload and published with a topic to the department MQTT broker via MQTT. This allows the data to be shared and subscribed by other devices/ services. Telegraf and InfluxDB were installed in the Raspberry Pi, Telegraf was configured to collect data from the related topics and send them to InfluxDB. Thus, the data is stored which allows comprehensive monitoring and time series analysis. Grafana was also installed in the Raspberry Pi and a dashboard was created for data visualization. This monitoring platform allows integration of data from multiple devices into a dashboard, which favours centralized monitoring and building management.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Estimating air change rate from CO₂ data

The air change rates recorded on Monday to Friday overnight typically lie between 0.15 – 0.22 h⁻¹. A similar air change rate of 0.22 h⁻¹ was also reported from a naturally ventilated office in a Malaysian University with window closed (Daghigh et al. 2008). The values for residential room with closed window were between 0.25 to 0.41 h⁻¹ in studied site in Israel and USA (Becker et al. 2014, Howard-Reed et al. 2002). However, the assumption of ventilation stays constant throughout the day is not guaranteed. During daytime occupants may open window or turn on the air conditioner. As a result, the air change rate obtained overnight may only best describe the window-closed scenario such as during winter but would underestimate the ventilation in other cases. Due to security and energy management reason, it was not possible to open window or turn on air conditioner overnight. If that was possible, air change rates in different scenarios would be measured, and the one that can best describe the daily condition would be applied. The CARA model is sensitive to changes in ventilation level, so relying on a fixed air change rate misses the opportunity to show the variation in risk from changing ventilation throughout a day (Figure 4.2).

On weekend the air change rates were observed to be 0.1 h⁻¹ or lower. That is because of the absence of occupant-generated CO₂ and consequently a small variation throughout the day. Some unanticipated records were observed in weekend. Occasionally the CO₂ reading at 7 a.m. were higher than that at 9 p.m. the night before, resulting in a negative air change rate. There were also occasions that the CO₂ readings were below 400 ppm, resulting in a computational error. These were tackled by implementing a conditional statement that will assign a predefined value if unanticipated results arise. Since the T6713 CO₂ Sensor Module has an accuracy of ± 25ppm or ± 3% of reading, when the room has a CO₂ concentration very close to ambient or when two values to be compared are very close, there may be a large relative error which could undermine the ventilation assessment.

The background ambient CO₂ is set as 400 ppm. This value may also require update as atmospheric CO₂ has risen from greenhouse effect and may have exceeded 400 ppm (Kahn 2016). Furthermore, urban area may have a higher CO₂ concentration than rural area, forming an urban CO₂ dome. Observation in Phoenix, Arizona, USA in January 2000 found that the CO₂ in city centre was on average 38-43% higher than the surrounding rural areas, with the peak difference reaching 75% (Idso et al., 2001). Since the classroom is next to Tottenham Court Road, a major road in central London, the outdoor CO₂ may exceed 400 ppm. This would upset the sensor calibration as well as calculation (see Appendix B). To improve accuracy the outdoor ambient CO₂ level can be measured and used for calculation if different from 400 ppm.

4.2 Using CO₂ data for direct airborne disease modelling

Depending on the number of occupants, activities performed and ventilation, indoor CO₂ concentration within a day can exhibit variation greater than 1500 ppm. This may not be visible during a short interval but would become apparent for a long interval such as 9 hours in a business day. As such, estimating infection probability for a long interval assuming the

current CO₂ level can represent the whole period, while having an advantage of only requiring the most recent updated variables and does not require data storage, would result in considerable variations within that period (Figure 4.1). This daily risk assessment tends to underestimate the overall risk in the morning when the CO₂ level is lower and overestimate that in the afternoon when CO₂ level is higher.

Figure 4.1 Graphical calculation of infection probability using Rudnick-Milton's model
(Total exposure time = 9 h, total number of occupants = 10, number of infectors = 1; plot generated using Math3d-react)

A second iteration was made to incorporate the variation in CO₂ into risk assessment. CO₂ levels over time are integrated and divided by the number of timestamps to obtain a representable average CO₂ concentration over a long interval. The average CO₂ level keeps including the newly updated values while reducing the weighting of each record when time passes. As a result, the risk a person experienced so far is captured in the integrative approach, and it is a better representation of the overall risk if one stays in the room for the entire day. Figure 4.2 shows the probability of infection for the current hour and the whole day obtained from both CARA and Rudnick-Milton's model for the without mask scenario, recorded every half an hour during a working day. Using an integrative approach results in a lower infection probability than using only the latest CO₂ for overall estimation, as well as a smaller fluctuation and a higher proximity to the result from CARA model, which is almost a constant. In addition, the figure demonstrates the CARA model is insensitive to variation of CO₂, while Rudnick-Milton's model depends very heavily on it. It also reveals that at the end of a working day, when the Rudnick-Milton's model has integrated all recorded CO₂ levels within the 9 hours, its overall infection probability is higher than that from the CARA model. Such difference may partially be attributed to the approach in treating virus loss through mechanisms besides ventilation such as biological decay and deposition. They were omitted in Rudnick-Milton's model but were accounted in CARA model. Note that the risk level obtained from the CARA model used an air change rate measured in a closed window scenario and might not be representable. If there was an improvement in ventilation, the risk level would be lower, resulting in an even greater difference in risk levels from the two models.

Figure 4.2 Probability of infection obtained from CARA and Rudnick-Milton's models from different time of a working day (11 August 2022, Thursday)

4.3 Visualization and communication

Each sensor device has a 4.2" (10.7 cm) e-Paper Display Module as the fundamental output display. E-Paper is similar to paper and provides a better visibility and visual comfort than an LCD screen, which may trigger visual fatigue (Benedetto et al. 2013). It is also much thinner and does not requiring electricity to hold figures or images. However, e-Paper has a lower refresh rate than an LCD screen and this would limitation user interactivity (Francis & Irikefe 2018). The e-Paper chosen has an adequate space to accommodate multiple figures and description. If a smaller display was employed, it would not be possible to display all information in one page while maintaining clarity. This would require either dropping of details such as description or splitting information into multiple slides. The former could lead to confusion or misunderstanding, while the later may undermine the intention to compare different scenarios as user may find it difficult to read and memorize different figures when the refresh of slides are either too fast or too slow.

While every device has an e-Paper display attached to show the risk assessment of the respective room, it is of management interest to oversee the conditions of all premises. A dashboard is created in Grafana as a centralized monitoring platform for the property management unit. While the standard tools in Grafana serve general purpose such as showing the trend over time or comparing between different sources, they do not show the spatial characteristic and relationship of data. The plugin *Flowcharting* was selected for its ability to display data on an overlay diagram. The plugin was installed on the Grafana plugin library in Raspberry Pi, after that a panel was created using flowcharting as one of the visualization methods. A floorplan was created in draw.io and imported into the panel to generate a graphical representation of the department. Semi-transparent layers were linked to selected variables (infection probability) so the colors and figures displayed will adjusted accordingly. The dashboard incorporates multiple visualization methods to enable a comprehensive view of the data (Figure 4.3).

Figure 4.3 Dashboard on Grafana

At present the dashboard only contain data from the two sensor devices (MK1 stands for iteration 1; MK2 for iteration 2 with a rotary encoder and time-weighted average Rudnick-Milton’s model) and the floorplan only highlights the airborne risk condition in the classroom as it is the only premise with device installed and data uploaded, but the system has the potential to incorporate multiple rooms within a floor, a building, or even a university complex (Figure 4.4). The floorplan-panel can be adapted to serve not only airborne risk assessment, but also other building management criteria such as thermal comfort, ventilation and energy consumption, with data fed from various sources of IoT devices.

Figure 4.4 A mimic diagram of the monitoring system showing airborne transmission risk in different rooms

4.4 User interactivity

The project has explored user interaction with the device. Attempts have been made to allow parameter values to be adjusted manually on the fly. The iteration 2 device has a rotary encoder button and was running a script with two interrupt functions, which were executed when a click event or a rotate event was listened, respectively. Clicking the button would

change the state from showing infection information to setting panel or vice versa. If the panel was in setting page, rotating the knob would change the parameter values, which were reflected on the display (Figure 4.5).

Figure 4.5 Changing parameter values using rotary encoder

The control works functionally, i.e., the display would react to the button click or switch rotate event, and the change in parameter values were recognized. However, the performance in user-experience was unfulfilling. Mainly, it took a while for the screen to response to the click or rotate event, and sometimes the event was not recognized. One possible explanation is that while the interrupt command gets execute instantly, it takes time for the loop to reach the display function. Together with the slow refresh rate of e-Paper, user may have an impression that the physical control and the digital display is out of sync.

Since the performance of manual setting may cause more confusion than satisfaction, it was not adopted. Instead, the button serves as a switch between showing the infection probability metrics from the CARA model and the model from Rudnick & Milton. Once the button interrupt is detected the state will change and the display will show either metric accordingly. The rotation interrupt function is blank and switching the rotary knob currently gives no effect. Nevertheless, this project has demonstrated it is possible to run an airborne disease transmission model with updated parameters obtained from sensors and input interruption. One may in the future explore the possibility to create a menu and enables change in settings on the fly, possibly with a more powerful microcontroller or/ and a display with a faster update time.

4.5 Occupancy estimation

Both the CARA and Rudnick-Milton's models have occupancy as a parameter, with the later greatly influenced by the number of total occupants in a room. In this project occupancy was a hypothetical value hard coded into the sketch. While the individual infection probability in CARA model does not show a variation with a change in total occupancy, it is an important parameter in Rudnick-Milton's model. Any change in CO₂ readings and subsequently the exhaled breath in indoor air with a fixed occupancy would either imply the ventilation rate or human activity level has changed and undermine the assessment. For a practical model this value should be set to best reflect the situation, such as using the occupant capacity, or a time-based variable decided by historical statistics or room usage. A more accurate approach would be supplying the model with real time occupancy monitoring or detection result. For premises that requires access card to enter/ exit, occupancy can be determined from the

access system. Furthermore, occupancy detection using various types of sensors and machine learning models has been studied, mainly for building energy and HVAC (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning) management purposes. For example, Wei et al. (2022) developed Faster region-based convolutional neural network models on an artificial intelligence (AI)-powered camera to detect number of occupants and occupancy activities. As human presence and activity are major sources of CO₂, studies have used different machine learning model to estimate occupancy such as time-delayed neural network (Han et al. 2013) and feature scaled extreme learning machine (Jiang et al. 2016). Estimation can also be made from multiple independent variables. For example, Ugwuanyi et al. (2021) applied gradient boosting for occupancy prediction using temperature, humidity, CO₂ concentration, noise, and pressure data. Wang et al. (2019) applied Adaptive Lasso model for feature extraction and identified temperature, CO₂ concentration, and Wi-Fi datasets together offer the optimal occupancy detection result. If occupancy is detected and shared, e.g., via MQTT, it can be subscribed by the microcontroller and used as a parameter value in the transmission model.

4.6 Additional physical devices

Apart from the sensor devices, alternative physical devices were further designed to explore risk communication in artistic, innovative, and inclusive aspect. They are not intended to be massively produced and deployed, but best served at specific occasions such as STEM workshops, colleges, or museums. The basic sensor devices target building managers and office users with a high level of numeracy by showing the transmission risk in numeric probability. However, people may not naturally think about risks numerically, and replacing statistics by qualitative representations may help risk perception (Steinhardt 2019). These alternative physical devices either embrace ambiguity by offering a categorical possibility instead of an absolute value or show risk with multiple levels of precision. This would help risk communication with audiences with low numeracy who often have troubles interpreting quantitative statement (Rakow et al.2015). The devices have no sensor components as they were designed as subsidiary devices, yet it is possible to upgrade them to self-contained sensor devices with sensor components. Risk information is obtained from MQTT and actuators would respond to the values based on predefined thresholds.

The idea of a COVID Risk Projector stemmed from the popular scientific demonstration of floating table tennis. A NodeMCU was connected to a MOSFET module which acts as a switch to bridge a 12V DC fan and external power supply (Figure 4.6). The fan speed was determined by the infection probability which was subscribed from MQTT and categorized into levels. As a result, the paper ball, which imitates a virion, would show an altitude and spinning fierceness corresponding to the infection probability. The vitality of the paper ball analogizes the likelihood of getting infected. The adoption of this device would also provide an opportunity to deliver STEM education in related topics such as transmissible disease and fluid mechanics.

Figure 4.6 COVID Risk Projector exterior (left) and interior (right)

Another design is a duo-gauge showing the risk in a with mask scenario against a without mask scenario. The gauge has characteristics in having a content-specific enclosure and a three-dimensional interior. A NodeMCU was connected to two servos, each rotates a plate and delivers the current risk class to the front (Figure 4.7).

Figure 4.7 Duo-gauge showing risk in with-mask and without-mask scenario

5. Conclusions

COVID-19 pandemic has caused severe loss of human life and socio-economic disruption. Risk assessment has an important role in policy making, such as back-to-office roadmap and mask mandate. It also guides building management such as ventilation. COVID Airborne Risk Assessment Calculator (CARA), originally developed as a web interface assessment tool, was extended by taking sensor data as inputs. Sensor devices were created, with each comprises a micro-controller, sensors for temperature, humidity and CO₂ concentration, as well as an e-Paper display. The internet of Things (IoT)-enhanced assessment tool can obtain updated and reliable data as inputs and provide a more reliable prediction. Besides CARA, a second model from Rudnick & Milton which is more lightweight and relies on CO₂ concentration was also applied. This study also explored the incorporation of indoor CO₂ in risk assessment. For CARA model ventilation rate was estimated by observing decay of CO₂ in the absence of source, while for Rudnick-Milton's model CO₂ was seen as a biomarker of exhaled breath and its concentration was directly used in risk calculation. Thus, this project demonstrates the suitability of running both comprehensive and simple models with micro-controller(s) and sensors. Further visualization and communication methods were explored, including a dashboard panel for building management, and alternative physical device for qualitative communication.

The devices short of having an occupancy estimate and a near real time ventilation assessment, which has a direct influence on Rudnick-Milton's model and the CARA model, respectively. This constraint the validity of the two models, for the CARA model the current air change rate estimate describes best the winter scenario and underestimates the ventilation in occasions when windows are opened or air conditioning is switched on; for the Rudnick-Milton's model a fixed number in occupancy with changing CO₂ levels would unintentionally be interpreted as a change in ventilation performance. Future works include the fusion of occupancy data from occupancy detection to a risk assessment variable, the improvement in the adequacy of air change rate estimation by considering multiple ventilation scenarios, as well as the development of a setting menu on sensor device that would enable user-friendly parameter values adjustment on the fly.

While this project focuses on risk assessment and communication of COVID-19, the approach and contents in sensing, deployment, and communication can be adapted to other airborne transmissible diseases. This project contributes by offering a prototype to accommodate transmission models and enhance their practicality, as well as streamlining the risk information process including sensor data capture, risk calculation, data visualization and communication.

6. References

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Appendix

A1. Further introduction of the CARA model

The CARA model estimates probability of infection using first principles with fundamental physics and physiology. It does not assume a steady state but estimates the concentration of virions over time which depends on the number and presence of the infected persons (source), ventilation and virological mechanisms (dispersion) (Figure A1).

In this project, the CARA model is enhanced by sensor devices which measure and input updated readings of temperature, humidity, and CO₂ concentration. CO₂ concentration is not a parameter in the CARA model (nor used as a proxy of air pollutant) since virion concentrations are calculated from first principles. Instead, in this work CO₂ was used to calculate ventilation rate which was then inputted into the model as the ventilation type 'measured ventilation' mentioned in chapter 3.4. Temperature and humidity are parameters for calculation of virus half-life, decay, and deposition. In the CARA model, indoor temperature is further used for computing temperature gradient and ventilation rate in a natural ventilation scenario (i.e., the opening of windows). Since the type of ventilation was set to 'measured ventilation' in this project, parameters related to natural ventilation including temperature was not used for this purpose.

Calculator

Simulation name:
E.g. Workshop without masks

Room number:
E.g. T7/R-033

Virus data:
Variant: SARS-CoV-2 (Delta VOC)

Room data:
 Room volume: Room volume (m³)
 Floor area: Room floor area (m²)
Ceiling height: Room ceiling height (m)
Central heating system in use: No Yes
Geographic location: Geneva, CHE

Ventilation data:
Ventilation type: No ventilation Mechanical Natural
HEPA filtration: No Yes
Flow rate (m³ / hour)

Face masks:
Are masks worn when occupants are at workstations?
 Yes No

Event data:
Total number of occupants: Number (#)
Number of infected people: 1
Activity type: Office

Exposed person(s) presence:
Start: 08:30 am Finish: 05:30 pm

Infected person(s) presence:
Start: 08:30 am Finish: 05:30 pm

Which month is the event? January

Activity breaks:
 Input separate breaks for infected and exposed person(s)
Lunch break: No Yes
Start: 12:30 pm Finish: 01:30 pm
Coffee Breaks: No breaks 2 4
Duration (minutes): 5
Coffee breaks are spread evenly throughout the day.

Generate report

Figure A1 The interface of the CARA web-based calculation tool

The CARA model supports graphical output in the form of a web interface which includes the probability of infection, expected number of new cases, and a plot showing mean concentration of virions, cumulative dose, and presence of exposed person(s) against time (Figure A2).

Figure A2 An example of the result section from the CARA web-based calculation tool

A2. Further discussion about CO₂ sensor used in this project

Telarie T6713 CO₂ Sensor Module was employed for CO₂ measurements in this project. This sensor is a non-dispersive infrared sensor (NDIR) which quantifies the concentration of CO₂ from the amount of light within a specific wavelength being detected in the two ends of the sensor. Compared with other types of CO₂ sensors (electrochemical sensor or metal oxide semiconductor sensor), a NDIR sensor measures actual CO₂ and will not be affected by the presence of other substances. For the other two types of sensors the readings will be affected by other substances, or even, the sensors do not actually target CO₂ but rely on volatile organic compounds (VOCs) as a proxy.

Another characteristic of this sensor is its ability to perform auto-calibration (Cooper 2016). The sensor will calibrate itself if exposed to the reference level at least three times per week. Since the self-calibration technique considers the reference value of CO₂ to be 400 ppm, if in practice the outside ambient is above 400 ppm, the sensor will report a value lower than the actual concentration by the difference between 400ppm and the reference level. This may affect the accuracy of the sensor and cause issues discussed in chapter 4.1.

Cooper, D. (2016). Telarie T67XX CO₂ Sensor Module – User Instructions Rev-003. Available at <http://www.co2meters.com/Documentation/Manuals/Manual-AMP-0002-T6713-Sensor.pdf> (Accessed: 10 August 2022)